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INCREASING THE CONTENT OF RECLAIMED ASPHALT IN ASPHALT MIXTURE BY USING REJUVENATORS

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Abstract. Recycling pavements is beneficial on various levels, since using reclaimed asphalt (RA) has a positive effect on the economy and environmental protection at the same time. Removed old asphalt pavement is no longer considered as a waste material, which has to be landfilled, but a useful material for further applications. Leading to a reduction of the need for virgin materials and preserve the planet. At the start, RA was used for construction of embankments and unbound granular layers, later cold recycling became another effective solution. After years of experiments, the rate of RA has increased to reach even the 100 %. But typical RA content in hot asphalt mixtures is between 25 % to 40 %. The presence of RA in the asphalt mixture has a negative effect on the mixture properties. Two alternatives were used in order to soften the aged bitumen – use of softer binder or special additives, i.e., rejuvenators. This study evaluated the possibility of increasing the RA content (30 % and 50 %) in asphalt mixture by adding mainly bio-based alternative rejuvenators. Mechanical performance was evaluated by means of laboratory investigations for typical characteristics dedicated to durability, stiffness, and cracking potential.

1. Introduction

The use of reclaimed asphalt (RA) in asphalt pavement has showed positive effect on the economy and environmental levels. It has showed a reduction in the consumption of virgin aggregates and virgin bituminous binder. Thus, providing an economic and environmental benefits. According to the European Asphalt Pavement Association (EAPA), the removed asphalt pavement in Europe is counted to 31.5×10^6 tons. In which, only 79 % was available to be used by the asphalt industry in 2020 [1]. This value represents the average quantity of 14 countries with variable data from one country to another. This variation is essentially due to the national regulation of each country.

Although these high recycling rate, the widely spread perception of these materials are the lower quality comparing to the virgin materials and various other mechanical concerns related to the asphalt mixture containing RA. Leading to a lack of confidence in using high content of RA in the production of asphalt concrete mixtures and thus, an increase in the RA stockpile inventory.

Originally, RA was used in the construction of embankment, unbound granular layers or as filling material for shoulders. After years of experiments, it was used in the construction of new roads and the percentage of the recycled materials was grown. Typically, the RA content is between 25 % and 40 % [2, 3]. Most frequently, asphalt plants use up to 20 % RA content in asphalt mixtures [4]. Since at low

RA content, the effect of aged bitumen from RA is minor. While, at high content, the aged binder blends with the new aggregates and affects the asphalt mixture performance properties [5]. The increase of the RA content in new asphalt mixtures implies an increase in the stiffness of the final asphalt mixture. This leads often to asphalt mixtures with less cracking resistance to fatigue, thermal change, and faster cracking propagation [6] – the asphalt mixture in general demonstrates a more brittle behaviour. This reduction in the mechanical performance properties may contribute to various forms of pavement deterioration like rutting and cracking [7, 8]. On the other hand, several studies have highlighted that adding RA in well-designed asphalt mixtures might result in mixtures with less water susceptibility and less prone to permanent deformation [9, 10, 11].

In order to increase the compatibility between the aged and the virgin aggregates and to soften the aged bitumen in the RA, two alternatives – softer virgin bitumen or recycling agents, i.e. rejuvenators, have been used by various studies and in practical applications since many years [5, 12, 13].

In 1960, asphalt rejuvenators were introduced as a restoration agent to the aged bitumen by making it softer and thus, lower its stiffness and restores its properties [14, 15, 3]. Many studies were carried out in studying the effects of the recycling agents – rejuvenators on the properties of the asphalt mixture containing RA. It was reported that the use of rejuvenators can enhance the moisture resistance, the mechanical properties, and workability of the recycled mixtures [16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21].

This research focuses on investigating the influence of increasing the RA content (30 % and 50 %) in asphalt mixture by adding bio-based alternative rejuvenators. The mechanical performance was evaluated by means of laboratory investigations for typical characteristics dedicated to durability, stiffness and cracking potential.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

To evaluate the influence of increasing the RA content in asphalt mixtures by means of adding bio-based alternative rejuvenators, a group of 14 mixtures were designed for the purpose. The experimental design of all the mixtures was in accordance with the typical asphalt concrete mix for the binder course with a Nominal Maximum Aggregate Size (NMAS) of 16 mm. Denoted as ACL 16 according to the Czech technical standard CSN 73 6121:2019.

In order to minimize the errors and to better understand the effectiveness of the different bio-based and recycled-base additives, the same aggregate, bitumen content and bitumen type (paving grade 50/70) were used for all mixtures. Six different bio-based rejuvenating agent types were applied in asphalt mixtures containing 30 % and 50 % RA. These agents were dosed with bituminous binder 50/70.

Table 1. Used rejuvenating agent and their dosage

Rejuvenating agent	Dosage of binder in RA (%)	Base of the rejuvenating agent
A	5	additive based on waste fats collected in wastewater treatment plants and/or in slaughterhouses (experimental product)
B	7	additive based on refined vegetable rapeseed oil and waste fats (experimental product)
C	7	additive based on refined vegetable rapeseed oil and used engine oil (experimental product)
RF	6	oil-based additive (commercial product)

SR	6	pine wood extract (lignin) based rejuvenator – a by-product of paper industry (commercial product)
AF	7	cationic surfactant based on phosphorous esters dissolved in fatty acid esters and paraffin oils

2.2. Test plan

To assess the performance of asphalt mixtures, a selection of laboratory tests was performed and examined:

- air voids content according to EN 12697-8,
- resistance to water immersion (ITSR) according to EN 12697-12 and to the water + one freezing cycle according to AASHTO T283 (modified procedure),
- determination of stiffness modulus according to EN 12697-26, Annex C – indirect tensile stress test method on cylindrical specimens (IT-CY),
- complex dynamic modulus according to EN 12697-26, Annex B – four point bending test on prismatic specimens (4PB-PR).

3. Test results

3.1. Air void content (EN 12697-8)

Figure 1 presents the air voids content of the Marshall test specimen. The air voids content of most of the mixtures, except the variant with 50 % RA and rejuvenator “A”, were within the limit 3~8 %. This implies that the addition of rejuvenating agent to the asphalt mixtures with RA exhibited a positive effect on the workability in the compaction process.

By comparing the influence of added rejuvenators on the different reclaimed asphalt ratios, it can be found that unlike the influence of the rejuvenators “A”, “B”, and “SR” which was similar for the variants with 30 % RA (a decrease by 1.5 % in air voids content), the later one have showed different effects in the variants with 50 % RA. It can be seen that “A” and “SR” have showed a greater influence (3.9 % and 2.7 % respectively) while “B” has showed a closer result (1.1 %).

Even though, the influence of the addition was diverse, it has engendered a decrease in the air voids content of AC mixtures. Thus, a better influence in the workability was found. The best result was exhibited by the rejuvenator “RF”.

Figure 1. Air voids content of asphalt mixture AC_{bin} containing respectively 30 % and 50 % RA (the red lines show the admissible interval for control testing requirements on voids content as applicable in the Czech Republic for AC_{bin} mixtures)

3.2. Stiffness modulus (EN 12697-26)

The stiffness modulus was conducted on Marshall test specimens by IT-CY test method at three test temperatures: 0 °C, 15 °C and 27 °C. Furthermore, the thermal susceptibility was calculated as a ratio of stiffness modulus at 0 °C and 27 °C. It is known that the lower the thermal susceptibility is, the less sensitive to temperature changes an asphalt mixture is, with respect to its deformation characteristics.

It is known that the addition of rejuvenating agents in reclaimed asphalt mixture should lower the stiffness modulus due to its rejuvenating properties. Similarly, a decrease in the RA content should lower the stiffness modulus due to the presence of less aged binder which tend to harden the mix. These facts were approved (see Figure 2).

An interesting result was shown by the mixtures with 30 % RA, where the stiffness modulus of all rejuvenated mixes has displayed similar values along the temperatures 15 °C and 27 °C. This indicates that around these two temperatures (15 °C and 27 °C), all rejuvenating agents function the same way regardless of their ratio or type. Yet, some variation in the stiffness modulus data were showed at 0 °C.

Similarly, most of the rejuvenating agents have showed similar effect on the mixtures with 50 % RA at the temperatures 15 °C and 27 °C. Except for the variants with “AF” which exhibited equal value to the referential mix.

The rejuvenator “A” has shown the best influence on the reclaimed asphalt mix containing 30 % RA. While the rejuvenator “B” has the best influence on the mixes with 50 % RA. Both statements apply, of course, to the selected contents of rejuvenators,

Even though, the stiffness modulus of the mixtures with 30 % RA were lower than the mixtures with 50 % RA, the thermal susceptibility values have shown an adverse effect to the thermal changes.

Figure 2. Stiffness modulus of asphalt mixture AC_{bin} containing respectively 30 % and 50 % RA and their thermal susceptibility

After testing the stiffness modulus, the asphalt mixtures were stored for 5 days in oven, with forced air circulation, at a temperature of 85 °C. The stiffness was measured again for further understanding to the effect of the ageing. It is known that under the effect of the ageing, the stiffness modulus of the mixtures tends to increase due to the hardening of the bituminous binder. This is where the use of rejuvenating agent should decrease the ageing rate.

On the other hand, the ageing index was calculated as a ratio between the aged and unaged stiffness modulus in order to study the susceptibility of the mix to ageing. The lower the ageing index is, the less susceptible to ageing the mix is. And thus, more durable.

Similar rejuvenators have exhibited different results (see Table 2) in accordance with the RA ratio, where some have shown an opposed effect between the two mixtures. For instance, the rejuvenator “C”

has showed the highest value of ageing index comparing to all mixes with 30 % RA at 15 °C. Thus, the less durable mixture. Yet, this rejuvenator had showed better results when it is added to AC mixtures with 50 % RA (keeping same dosage of the rejuvenator). Alternatively, the addition of the rejuvenator “RF” has the best results on both group of mixtures.

Besides, it is clear that the effect of the rejuvenators to the ageing depends on the RA content in the mixture. While the effect is better demonstrated in the mixtures containing 50 % RA at 15 °C, it is almost not observed for the mixtures with 30 % RA at the same temperatures.

Table 2. Stiffness modulus of aged asphalt mixture AC_{bin} containing respectively 30 % and 50 % RA and the ageing index

		Stiffness modulus [MPa]		Ageing index [-]	
		AGED 0 °C	AGED 15 °C	0 °C	15 °C
30 % RA	50/70	-	17 614	-	1.15
	5 % A	19 934	11 574	1.11	1.19
	7 % B	-	13 338	-	1.19
	7 % C	-	12 799	-	1.27
	6 % RF	20 205	11 746	0.99	1.16
	6 % SR	21 672	12 422	1.04	1.15
	7 % AF	20 033	12 468	1.08	1.15
50 % RA	50/70	27 734	21 378	1.01	1.22
	5 % A	25 955	13 933	1.19	1.18
	7 % B	26 598	11 981	1.27	1.14
	7 % C	27 873	14 827	1.21	1.14
	6 % RF	23 844	12 522	1.01	1.03
	6 % SR	26 899	15 273	1.18	1.23
	7 % AF	27 288	19 283	1.08	1.16

3.3. Moisture susceptibility and freezing and thawing (EN 12697-12 - AASHTO T283-3)

The water susceptibility test was performed according to the standard EN 12697-12. Whereas the freezing and the thawing test was performed according to the AASHTO T283-3. The specimens were tested at a temperature of 15 °C and at a loading rate of 50 mm/min according to EN 12697-23 on universal Marshall press.

Figure 3. Indirect tensile strength (ITS) dry of asphalt mixture AC_{bin} containing respectively 30 % and 50 % RA

Based on the analysis of the ITS of the dry specimens (Figure 3), it was observed that similarly to the stiffness modulus at 15 °C, the ITS values of the set of specimens with 30 % RA were almost equal for all the rejuvenating mixtures. However, the decrease of their value in comparison to the referential mixture was almost negligible as it was shown for stiffness. This result was also confirmed in the study [22]. Unexpectedly, the effect of the added rejuvenators on the ITS values were different than the stiffness for the set of mixtures with 50 % RA.

Following to the ITSR values (Table 3) of the analysed mixtures, a similarity in the effect of the added rejuvenating agents was noticed according the EN test method regardless the RA ratio in the reclaimed mixtures. Except for the rejuvenators “SR” and “AF” which showed an increase in the ITSR values comparing to the referential for the set of mixtures with 50 % RA, and a decrease for the set of mixtures with 30 % RA. As for the ITSR values according to AASHTO T283 protocol, only the rejuvenator “SR” has displayed a similar influence in both group of mixtures.

Table 3. Indirect tensile strength (ITS) and ratio (ITSR) of asphalt mixture AC_{bin} 16 containing respectively 30 % and 50 % RA

		Indirect tensile strength [MPa]			ITSR _{EN}	ITSR _{AASHTO}
		R _{dry}	R _{EN}	R _{AASHTO}		
30 % RA	50/70	2.43	1.94	1.99	79.7%	81.8%
	5 % A	1.94	1.74	1.48	89.8%	76.6%
	7 % B	2.17	1.72	1.58	79.3%	72.6%
	7 % C	2.07	1.62	1.59	78.3%	76.9%
	6 % RF	1.80	1.68	1.64	93.2%	90.8%
	6 % SR	2.24	1.73	1.77	77.4%	79.2%
	7 % AF	2.32	1.85	1.71	79.5%	73.6%
50 % RA	50/70	3.05	2.43	2.19	79.6%	71.7%
	5 % A	2.64	2.39	2.29	90.0%	86.0%
	7 % B	1.91	1.47	1.57	77.0%	82.0%
	7 % C	2.10	1.71	1.76	82.0%	84.0%
	6 % RF	2.71	2.57	2.53	94.8%	93.3%
	6 % SR	2.50	2.27	1.89	90.7%	75.5%
	7 % AF	2.47	2.32	2.23	93.9%	90.2%

3.4. Complex dynamic modulus (EN 12697-26)

The dynamic modulus test was performed on prismatic beam specimens by four point bending beam (4PB-PR) test method. The test was conducted at four temperatures 0 °C, 10 °C, 20 °C, and 30 °C, and eleven selected test frequencies 50, 30, 20, 15, 10, 8, 5, 3, 2, 1 and 0.1 Hz for each temperature. Master curves of all mixtures as shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5 were constructed using the principle of time-temperature superposition and a reference temperature of 20 °C.

Different rejuvenators have shown different effect with respect to the reclaimed asphalt content and the range of frequency/temperature at which it was tested.

As it was mentioned above, the addition of these rejuvenating agents intends to lower the dynamic modulus due to its rejuvenating properties – the effect shall be similar to expectations for stiffness. This result was given by all the used rejuvenators in both group of assessed asphalt mixtures containing

reclaimed asphalt. Surprisingly, the additive “SR” has opposite effect at the range of high frequency/low temperature within the asphalt mixture with 30 % RA if compared to the variant with higher RA content. From the waveform of master curve, it seems that for the 50 % RA variant the thermal susceptibility might be lower.

Figure 4. Master curve of the 4PB dynamic modulus of asphalt mixtures with 30 % RA

Figure 5. Master curve of the 4PB dynamic modulus of reclaimed mixtures with 50 % RA

Contrarily to the stiffness results, where all the modulus values of the 30 % RA group have indicated lower results than the stiffness values of the group with 50 % RA at all temperatures, the dynamic modulus has shown diverse results depending on the type of the tested additive (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Comparison between the master curves AC mixtures with 30 % RA vs. AC mixtures with 50 % RA

4. Conclusion

This paper was dedicated to the study of the possibility of increasing RA content in asphalt mixtures by using mainly bio-based rejuvenating agents. The addition of RA makes the asphalt mixture stiffer due to the aged bitumen in the mix. The solution was to add alternative rejuvenators. The effect of these added rejuvenators was compared for two RA contents (30 % RA and 50 % RA) in the same type of asphalt mixture. Mainly strain characteristics and moisture susceptibility are presented in this paper.

Most of the mixtures have shown better compactibility since the air voids content was decreasing. Results proved that the addition of rejuvenating agents made asphalt mixtures with elevated RA content less stiff. The results of the stiffness modulus as well as the dynamic modulus of most of the rejuvenated

mixtures were decreasing comparing to the referential mix (asphalt mixture containing reclaimed asphalt but with neither softer binder nor rejuvenator).

The results of indirect tensile strength of unsaturated (dry) test specimens were consistent with those to the stiffness at 15 °C, i.e., that the ITS values decreased with the addition of rejuvenators.

However, the effect of these rejuvenators was very different for both groups of asphalt, i.e., for mixtures with 30 % RA and mixtures with 50 % RA. Thus, it is not possible to conclude on the effect of the rejuvenating agents on the asphalt mixtures with RA. This might be related to the ability of the diffusion of various rejuvenators and their dependence on ageing degree of the binder to be rejuvenated and the content of such bitumen (see e.g. [22]). Therefore, the choice of the “right” additive will be in accordance with the targeted-to-be-improved parameter.

An interesting result were presented by the addition of rejuvenators in the group of reclaimed mixtures with 30 % RA, where the results were similar regardless the type of the rejuvenator. This result can be due to the low content of reclaimed asphalt added to the designed mixture.

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References

- [1] European Asphalt Pavement Association—EAPA, "Asphalt in figures 2020," EAPA, Brussels, 2020.
- [2] X. Li, M. O. Marasteanu, R. C. Williams and T. R. Clyne, "Effect of reclaimed asphalt pavement (proportion and type) and binder grade on asphalt mixtures.," *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, pp. 90-97, 2008.
- [3] P. S. Lin, T. L. Wu, C. W. Chang and B. Y. Chou, "Effects of recycling agents on aged asphalt binders and reclaimed asphalt concrete.," *Materials and Structures*, p. 911–921, 2011.
- [4] European Committee for Standardization (CEN), "Bituminous mixtures – Materials specifications – Part 1: Asphalt Concrete.," 2008.
- [5] R. S. McDaniel, H. Soleymani, R. M. Anderson, P. Turner and R. Peterson, *Recommended use of reclaimed asphalt pavement in the Superpave mix design method.*, National Cooperative Highway Research Program (NCHRP), 2000.
- [6] J. R. Willis, P. Turner, G. Julian, A. J. Taylor, N. Tran and G. F. De Padula, "Effects of changing virgin binder grade," NCAT Report No. 12-03; National Center for Asphalt Technology: , Auburn, AL, USA, 2012.
- [7] M. Solaimanian, T. W. Kennedy and W. E. Elmore, "Long-term evaluation of stripping and moisture damage in asphalt pavements treated with lime and antistripping agents," Texas Department of Transportation, Texas, USA, 1993.
- [8] N. C. Krutz and M. Stroup-Gardiner, "Relationship between permanent deformation of asphalt concrete and moisture sensitivity," *Chip seals, friction courses, and asphalt pavement rutting*, Transportation Research Board, pp. 169-177, 1990.
- [9] M. Zaumanis and R. B. Mallick, "Review of very high-content reclaimed asphalt use in plant-produced pavements: state of the art," *International Journal of Pavement Engineering*, p. 39–55, 2014.
- [10] F. Zhou, S. Hu, G. Das and T. Scullion, "High RAP Mixes Design Methodology with Balanced

- Performance," Texas Transportation Institute: College Station, TX, USA, 2011.
- [11] R. Karlsson and U. Isacson, "Material-related aspects of asphalt recycling—State of the art," *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, p. 81–92, 2006.
- [12] N. H. Tran, A. Taylor and R. Willis, "Effect of rejuvenator on performance properties of HMA," National Center for Asphalt Technology, Auburn, AL, USA, 2012.
- [13] A. J. d. Barco Carrión, D. Lo Presti, S. Pouget, G. Airey and E. Chailleux, "Linear viscoelastic properties of high reclaimed asphalt content mixes with biobinders," *Road Materials and Pavement Design*, p. 241–251, 2017.
- [14] J. Shen, S. Amirkhanian and B. Tang, "Effects of rejuvenator on performance-based properties of rejuvenated asphalt binder and mixtures," *Construction and Building Materials*, pp. 958–964, 2007.
- [15] R. Romera, A. Santamaría, J. J. Peña, M. E. Muñoz, M. Barral, E. García and V. Jañez, "Rheological aspects of the rejuvenation of aged bitumen," *Rheologica Acta*, p. 474–478, 2006.
- [16] A. M. El-Shorbagy, S. M. El-Badawy and A. R. Gabr, "Investigation of waste oils as rejuvenators of aged bitumen for sustainable pavement," *Construction and Building Materials*, pp. 228–237, 2019.
- [17] A. Wozzuk, M. Wróbel and W. Franus, "Influence of waste engine oil addition on the properties of zeolite-foamed asphalt," *Materials*, p. 2265, 2019.
- [18] M. A. Jain, A. Sharma and D. K. Sharma, "Use of edible oil as rejuvenator in reclaimed asphalt pavement," the a National Conference on Roads and Transport (NCORT-2017), 14–15 October 2017.
- [19] J. M. Yu., Y. F. Guo, L. Peng, F. Guo and H. Y. Yu, "Rejuvenating effect of soft bitumen, liquid surfactant and bio-rejuvenator on artificial aged asphalt," *Construction and Building Materials*, p. 119336, 2020.
- [20] K. A. Ahmad, M. E. Abdullah, N. A. Hassan, N. Usman, R. M. Hassan, M. A. Bilema, S. M. Saeed and A. Batari, "Effect of bio based rejuvenator on mix design, energy consumption and GHG emission of high RAP mixture," the 4th International Conference on Civil and Environmental Engineering for Sustainability (IConCEES 2017), 4–5 December 2017.
- [21] M. H. Gong, J. Yang, J. Y. Yang, H. R. Zhu and T. Z. Tong, "Physical–chemical properties of aged asphalt rejuvenated by bio-oil derived from biodiesel residue," *Construction and Building Materials*, pp. 35–45, 2016.
- [22] L. Ržek, . M. . R. Turk and M. Tušar, "Increasing the rate of reclaimed asphalt in asphalt mixture by using alternative rejuvenator produced by tire pyrolysis" *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 232, p. 117177, 30 January 2020.